

The impact of intergenerational embeddedness on the mental health of university instructors

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Purpose

Measuring health behaviour and supporting health development is getting more attendance in higher education. It is well-known that the influence of the environment where students study can affect every part of life including academic achievement, friendships, health awareness and behaviour etc. Thus, the effect of the higher educational institution is visible regarding social life and academic and non-academic achievement as well. Researches focusing on campus impact have stated that the effect of the higher education institution depends on the level of the student integration (Tinto, 1993; Astin, 1999; Pusztai, 2015). The integration of the students has educational and social dimensions which include intergenerational and intragenerational relationships in connection with the higher educational institute (Tinto, 1993). Intragenerational network reflects on the relationships with peers while intergenerational network includes relationships with university staff. Previous researches claim that student-faculty relationship is supportive regarding their attrition and academic achievement (Pascarella & Terenzini, 2005; Pusztai, 2015) and their health-protective behaviour including sporting habits (Pusztai et al., 2017). Having a close relationship with instructors can motivate students to engage in the life of the university or the faculty. They are usually more involved in programs organised by the institute where they learn including academic and non-academic programs. In our previous research, we found that close relationships with instructors have a weakening effect on students' (elite) sport motivation, as these relationships are likely to lead students in a different direction, typically towards the worlds of science and culture (Kovács et al., 2022).

The main aim of our study is to investigate the teacher-student relationship in a higher educational context to discover its possible supporting impact on the mental health of university lecturers. We plan to conduct a survey among university lecturers focusing on their mental health. We aim to investigate their well-being, the level of satisfaction, trust in the institution and their relationship network including their colleagues and students as well. Psychological questionnaires (Perceived Stress Scale, Cohen et al., 1983; WHO-WBI, Topp et al., 2015) and close-ended questions for investigating the teacher-student relationship (e.g. How many students do you have with whom you can talk about sport / culture etc.?) are planned to be used. We hypothesise that similar to the supportive impact of intergenerational relationship on students' academic and non-academic achievement, it will have a positive impact on the mental health of the university lecturers as well, increasing their well-being and level of satisfaction and decreasing their burnout. We suppose that better relationship network with students is also parallel with the higher level of engagement toward the institute and the university.

Implications

Regarding the long-term well-being of the society, the responsibility of higher educational institutions is limited not only on education of intellectuals but it plays an important role in development of health and life quality as well. Universities and colleges mean the health-constructing area for their students and employees which is a determinant part of everyday life as well as these stages helps to reach the best possible health condition and the learn and fix the

necessary patterns (NEFI, 2017). Therefore, based on our results, we plan to create a training programme for university lecturers to support them in strengthening their relationship with their students.

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Resources

- Astin, A. W. (1999). Student involvement: A developmental theory for higher education. *Journal of College Student Development*, 40(5), 518.
- Cohen, S., Kamarck, T., & Mermelstein, R. (1983). A global measure of perceived stress. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 24(4), 385–396.
- Kovács, K. E., Kovács, K., Szabó, F., Dan, B. A., Szakál, Z., Moravec, M., Szabó, D., Olajos, T., Csukonyi, C., Papp, D., Órsi, B., & Pusztai, G. (2022). Sport motivation from the perspective of health, institutional embeddedness and academic persistence among higher educational students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(12), 7423. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19127423>
- Pusztai, G., Kovács, K., Kovács, K. E., & Nagy, B. E. (2018). The effect of campus environment on students' health behaviour in four Central European countries. *Journal of Social Research and Policy*, 8(1), 125-138.
- NEFI (2017). Egészségjelentés 2016. Budapest, Nemzeti Egészségfejlesztési Intézet. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316684736_Egeszsegjelentes2016_Health_Report_2016
- Pascarella, E. T., & Terenzini, P. T. (2005). *How College Affects Students: A Third Decade of Research*. San Francisco: John Wiley and Sons.
- Pusztai G. (2015). *Pathways to Success in Higher Education: rethinking the social capital theory in the light of institutional diversity*. Frankfurt am Main, Peter Lang.
- Tinto, V. (1993). *Leaving college. Rethinking the Causes and Cures of Student Attrition*. Chicago–London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Topp, C. W., Østergaard, S. D., Søndergaard, S., & Bech, P. (2015). The who-5 well-being index: A systematic review of the literature. *Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics*, 84(3), 167–176. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000376585>

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